

Umma Kalada of the Loura Indigenous Community as a Living Museum in Teaching Social Studies in Elementary School

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 05, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: August 06, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Social Studies, Living Museum, Ummakalada</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6968630</p>	<p><i>The research was conducted with two objectives, namely, first: to find and analyze social studies learning materials contained in the ummakalada of the Loura aborigines. Second: the way in which Living Museum Learning is implemented in social science learning in elementary school. The research method used is an ethnographic approach. The data were obtained by interviewing sources who still hold local beliefs (Marapu). The ummakalada of the Loura aborigines has been found to be a traditional house that has been maintained to this day since the ancestors or the first people to occupy the Loura area. UmmaKalada as a learning resource to teach social science topics about social interaction, economic activities, culture, natural resources and religion. The form of implementing social science learning by using UmmaKalada as a living museum or learning resource is the study tour method.</i></p>

Introduction

Teaching social studies to elementary school students means teaching several integrated social studies disciplines such as political science, sociology, history, economics, geography, anthropology, including humanities (Somantri, 2001) and even science (Savage & Armstrong, 1996). Social Studies is part of the school curriculum responsible for supporting students to develop the knowledge, skills and values needed to play an active role in community life locally, nationally and globally. Social studies aimsto prepare students to become good citizens who have the knowledge, values, and skills (Sapriya, 2014; Banks, 1985; Jarolimek, J. and Parker, W.C. 1993).

Social studies knowledge, values, and skills taught to students constitute a comprehensive skill for making students good citizens (Banks, 1985). Students must have knowledge to act in the civic community and make effective decisions. As citizens, students must develop a commitment to democratic and human values. Meanwhile, the skills required by students include thinking skills, social science research skills, academic skills, and group life skills.

In order to fulfill the educational mandate for social studies, the Indonesian State Curriculum Center compiles the amount of social studies education that must be taught to students from elementary to high school. The scope of social studies includes aspects, 1) people, place and environment, 2) time, sustainability and change, 3) social and cultural systems, 4) economic behavior and welfare. The scope will provide students with facts, concepts and theories in the area, in the country and worldwide.

At the stage of teaching social studies to students, an approach appropriate to the level of education is required. Elementary school students need a more contextual approach to learning than high school students (Asrial, et al, 2019). The current curriculum in Indonesia requires teachers to create effective learning by imparting knowledge, attitudes and life skills to students. The students' socio-cultural environment is the most appropriate choice for using a contextual approach (Pantic, N. and Wubbels, T., 2012; Unlu, Sahika.. 2018). Additionally, a teacher must be mindful of student cultural diversity so that learning takes advantage of student cultural diversity (Hernández, J.C., et al, 2021). Using socioculture as a learning approach is known as an ethnopedagogical approach (Muzakkir. 2021; Alwasilan. A. 2009).

Ethnopedagogy is a learning approach that explores local cultural values and is internalized in learning (Muzakkir. 2021). Also known as culture-based learning(Alexander, 2001). With this approach, students will easily understand the lesson and learn more about the culture so as not to be uprooted by the culture. So that students have knowledge, attitudes and skills derived from the culture. Hafid, et al. (2015) claimed that ethnopedagogy elevates the values of local wisdom as an important part of the educational process, as part of the civilization process. Furthermore, in the escalation of increasingly dynamic social interactions due to various issues that trigger the emergence of conflicts, ethnopedagogy is also placed as a differences-based learning model to find unification efforts within the differences themselves. Education through an ethnopedagogical approach sees local knowledge as a source of innovation and skills that can be strengthened (Priadi S, 2011). In

fact, local wisdom is not infrequently used as local decision-making, as is the case in the area of natural resource management and various other social activities in community life (Lukong, T.E., Njamfa, T., & Jaja, 2018).

Traditional houses are one of the elements of culture in Indonesia. Each region or region has a different traditional house, both in terms of naming and function. Traditional houses in Indonesia are the nation's cultural wealth (Amir & Abraham, 2016). which is maintained to this day. One of the traditional houses that survives today is *UmmaKalada*. *Ummakalada* is the traditional house of the people of Sumba island. *UmmaKalada* as the first home of the people who inhabited the island of Sumba. The first people to inhabit the island of Sumba have a belief or religion known as the Marapu (Budianto, A & Karo, R.K, 2021). *UmmaKalada* is like a place of worship or performing marapu belief rituals. The number of *UmmaKalada* in a settlement or village (*WannoKalada*) is determined by the number of people inhabiting the area. The current existence of the *UmmaKalada* is the identity of the people of the island of Sumba, including the indigenous Loura community in the western region or Southwest Sumba District, where the *UmmaKalada* is located in the village of Karuni. *UmmaKalada* extends over eight villages (*WannoKalada*). An *ummakalada* represents the tribe in the Loura area.

Cultural values passed through *UmmaKalada* or local culture were not used as a source for contextual learning. This is due to teachers' lack of ability to design learning based on local culture (Oktavianti&Yuni R. 2018), teachers use lecture style and there is no way to conduct reflective research to improve learning process. Another consequence is that the preservation of local culture is far from what is expected (Ridwan. 2014).

In response to the above issues, a study was conducted to make *UmmaKalada* a resource for learning social studies in elementary schools. *Ummakalada* as an ancestral heritage maintained to this day, so it is necessary to analyze the material or content of social studies learning in elementary school with the local culture found in *ummakalada*. Due to the existence of *ummakalada* to this day, the offer of teaching elementary social studies for primary school children is intended to make *ummakalada* a living museum.

Living museums present things that are still preserved in particular communities, whether they be life views, sociocultures, or centuries-old cultural assets (Supriatna, N &Pageh, 2022; Hooper, E & Greenhill, 2007; Nuhayah&Wawan, 2021). Living Museum is a museum concept that contains human life in the present and describes part of the process of past life. The Living Museum is an area that contains the authenticity of a society's historical and cultural values and lives with the people who inhabit it (Hanggara&Ramdlani, 2015; Susilo, D., Nana, S, &Kustono, 2021). The living museum presents things that exist in the local community, or in other words, visitors go on guided tours or visits and learn directly from local people who still maintain traditions of their ancestors.

This living museum is an introductory medium for students about ethnicity and culture, creating an attitude of respect, respect and tolerance. By providing real examples that exist in surrounding life, a new mindset is created and cultural values continue to be passed on (Jonas N., Simon K. & Scott Reeves, 2013). Through the living museum, students learn collaboratively, between students and with the local community. This makes learning more active and fun (Nurdiansah., et.al. 2021)

Based on the first study mentioned above, this paper has two aims. The first objective: to find and analyze social studies learning materials found in the *UmmaKalada* of the Loura Indians. The second goal: the form of implementation of living museum learning in social studies learning in elementary school.

Method

The research was conducted using ethnographic methods. The ethnographic method is a type of qualitative research that aims to investigate problems based on deep traditions about social or human problems in a particular group (Creswell, J. W, 2010). The research was conducted on indigenous peoples in eight villages (*wannokalada*) from December 2020 to September 2021. Research informants are indigenous peoples who still maintain *ummakalada*, informants selected based on a preliminary study to find out community leaders who still maintain *ummakalada*. Data were collected by means of interviews, observation and documentation as well as conducting a review of related literature. Data validity was carried out with five of the eight strategies suggested by Creswell (2008). The five strategies include: triangulate, member checking, rich and thick description), sharing with fellow researchers or peer the briefing experts. The data collected was then analyzed using an interactive model from Miles and Huberman (1989) which includes data collection, data reduction, data display, and drawing conclusions.

Results and Discussion

UmmaKalada and the indigenous people of Loura

The Loura indigenous people live in Karuni village, Southwest Sumba District. Some people still maintain the local belief, namely "*Marapu*". *Marapu*, is the original belief of ancient humans on the island of Sumba including the Loura indigenous people who still survive to this day. *Marapu* belief includes spirits, gods or goddesses, ancestral spirits, magical powers, medicines which are believed to affect human life. Adherents of

the *Marapub* belief are called "*AtabaraMarapu*". *AtabaraMarapu* lives in a traditional village known as *WannoKalada* (big village). *Wannokalada* is the village of the indigenous people of Loura or Sumba.

The existence of *WannoKalada* is marked by the number of traditional houses (*ummakalada*). One *ummakalada* represents one tribe (*Kabizzu*) in Loura. So that houses and villages in the Loura community cannot be separated because a village (*wannokalada*) consists of houses (*ummakalada*).

Figure.1. ummakalada of the Indigenous people of Loura in WannoKalada Bukaregha

It is called *ummakalada* because of its function as a gathering place or central for all tribal members (*kabizzu*) scattered around the Loura area or outside Sumba Island to carry out spiritual, cultural and social activities. Like every new born baby, it must be under the customary village to receive blessings from the *ummakalada* in this case the ancestors and also as a census of new residents in the tribe.

Physically, the traditional house or *ummakalada* of the Loura indigenous people is made using local building materials or from nature. The roof is made of thatch, the frame of the house is made of wood and bamboo, as well as stone as a fence or pet cage. *Ummakalada* is occupied by the nuclear family of *RatoAdat* or an priest who has been jointly appointed by tribal members. *Ummakalada* also keeps heirlooms that are hundreds and even thousands of years old. The horns of the buffalo and the jaws of the pigs sacrificed during the *Marapu* ritual are arranged in such a way on the *ummakalada* as evidence or stories for the next generation. In front of the traditional house there is a stone grave as a burial place for the ancestors or the first humans of the *kabizzu*. So that every member of the *kabizzu* who visits *ummakalada* always keeps areca and betel on the grave or grave stone as a sign or prayer to ask for "*Maringi-malala*" (blessing-hospitality)

Ummakalada consists of three levels with different functions of each level. The first level (*kallikabunga*) is the ground level which functions as a place for pets such as buffalo, horses, cows, pigs, and goats. The second level (*padouatapia*) is the level as a place for human activities such as cooking, eating, traditional ritual activities where heirlooms are stored. The third level (*ummandana*) or a kind of attic for storing food supplies and plant seeds or can be called a warehouse.

The topic of social studies learning at UmmaKalada as a Living Museum

Social studies learning materials and resources in elementary schools at the Loura indigenous community which can be used as living museums are described in the following table.

Table 1. Social studies material in elementary schools and living museums at UmmaKalada

Social Studies Material	Living museum at ummakalada
<i>Culture</i>	art, traditional clothing, language, ancestral heritage objects (<i>bendaPusaka</i>), megalithic graves
<i>economic activity</i>	Agriculture (<i>parappona</i>), lending of goods or money (<i>paande</i>), animal husbandry (<i>rangaumma</i>)
<i>Natural resources</i>	Views on natural resources and their use
<i>Religion</i>	Contents of the teachings of the <i>Marapu</i> faith
<i>Social Group</i>	the number of ummakalada (<i>kabizzu</i>) in the village (<i>wannokalada</i>)

1. Culture

Ummakalada is the center of *marapu* belief ritual activities for all the tribes in the Loura area. In these traditional ritual activities, various kinds of dances or arts (*Nego-kabana*) will be displayed accompanied by traditional music that is beaten (*talla*) with a certain rhythm. With regard to traditional clothing in everyday life and traditional activities, the clothes used are woven with various motifs. The women use a sarong (*pawee*) with

beads hanging on the neck (*muti*), earrings (*mamoli*), woven pandan bags (*kaleku*) and wristbands (*lele*). While men use cloth wrapped around the waist (*kalabo*) with a machete tucked in (*katopo*) and head straps (*kapouta*).

In addition, every *ummakalada* has heirlooms or ancient objects inherited by their ancestors in the form of beads, jars, swords or sticks made of gold and bronze. These heirlooms can only be seen at events or rituals. There is also a megalithic grave (*oddi*) in each *ummakalada*. Graves are an inseparable part of the *ummakalada*. The indigenous people of Loura have the view that the graves is a second home after death. *Oddiare* places where the ancestors or first people of the tribe or *kabizzuare* buried. The grave can also be used as a medium to tell children or the next generation the history of tribal or *kabizu* trips. Please note that one grave can be used for several tribe members who died from several generations.

2. Economic Activities

The economic activities of the Loura indigenous people adhere to a kinship. There are agricultural activities, livestock, as well as a system of borrowing goods and money. In agricultural activities, the community adheres to the *parappona* system. *Parapponais* a form of cooperation in gardening. each relative gets a turn or schedule for managing the garden. Carried out together with relatives in one *wannokalada*. Farming activities in *ummakalada* are known as tribal or sacred animals (*rangaumma*) and pets in general (*rangataguata pia*). *Rangaumma* cannot be traded, only for traditional rituals, the animal forms are buffalo and horse. Meanwhile, *Rangataguata pia* is a pet that can be used for family economic purposes such as horses, buffalo, goats, chickens, and pigs. There is a borrowing system or mode for the Loura indigenous people, namely *pa'ande* and *madarra*. *Pa'ande* is a system of borrowing goods or money with a return system based on an agreement between two parties. While *madarra* is a system of asking for help from others without having to be returned.

3. Natural Resources

The indigenous people of Loura have the view that nature is a very important part of humans. So there are *marapuomma* and *marapumaradakadahu*. *Marapuomma* is a spirit or god who specifically cares for and fulfills human needs in terms of agriculture. Rice and corn are staple crops for vegetable needs. While *marapumaradakadahu* is a spirit or god who guards the fields and forests. Utilization of the field (*marada*) as a place for raising large animals and weeds as roofing material or covering traditional houses. In addition, megalithic tomb stones were obtained from *Marada*. while the forest (*kadahu*) as a hunting ground and as a place to obtain materials for making traditional houses such as ropes and poles for traditional houses. The Loura indigenous people also take advantage of natural resources sourced from the sea or the coast. Salt is made traditionally by boiling sea water (*patiinamei*) until it crystallizes and produces salt. The Loura indigenous people also look for fish or seafood at low tide (*marra*). Due to the dependence of indigenous peoples on nature, animal sculptures are found on the poles of traditional houses and graves and are used as motifs for woven fabrics. To preserve the natural environment, the indigenous people of Loura apply forest or forbidden fields (*marada-kadahuerri*).

4. Religion

The indigenous people of Loura still adhere to the local religion, namely *Marapu*. *Marapu* is a local belief that is recognized and recorded as a belief in one God. Although called adherents of *marapu* (*atabarramarapu*) but it is believed that every *ummakalada* has its own *marapu*. Some pray to springs, fields, and certain animals. Therefore, in one village there is a diversity of *marapu* beliefs. The ritual activities of the *marapu* beliefs are *woleka*, *zaizo*, *urrata*, and *kerita*. The priest of *ata bara marapu* is *Rato*.

5. Social groups

Men in the view of the indigenous people of Loura occupy a high position. This is supported by the patriarchal system. Each *ummakalada* is inhabited by one family and even more. Boys who are already married can stay in the house until a decision is made to build their own house. In addition, if there is a daughter who is married but has not completed the marriage custom, her husband will also live in the house known as term *pangera*. The parents of the head of the family in certain situations will also live in the house. So in one *ummakalada* or house a small social group has been formed.

In addition, the existence of *ummakalada* in one village will form a wider social group. Togetherness (*paiana*) is a characteristic of one village. The social class of the indigenous people of Sumba is generally divided into two, namely the *tokko* (kings) and the *atamilla* (common people). The nobility class (*tokko*) is characterized by the ownership of many pets and large land. land is very limited. In one *ummakalada* or tribe there is a division of sub-tribes.

UmmaKalada's Potential as a Living Museum

The *ummakalada* of the Loura indigenous community which is still maintained to this day can be used as a learning resource for elementary social studies. Utilization by making *ummakalada* as a living museum. As a living museum because *ummakalada* is a form of heritage from the ancestors that is still maintained its authenticity to this day. It is not only the physical form of the house or community that is preserved but also the values contained therein. Students are invited to directly experience while learning by visiting *ummakalada* in *WannoKalada*. One of the learning activities directly in the field is by applying the study tour method. The study tour method is a way of learning by inviting students to come down directly in the surrounding

environment or field by involving all the senses. Students learn with recreational nuances. Students can see the object being studied up close (Sujana, 2011; Suprijanto, 2009)

The study tour method can be applied in elementary schools located in the Loura sub-district and the Tambolaka city sub-district, Southwest Sumba Regency. The elementary schools located in the two sub-districts are geographically quite close to the location of the *ummakalada*, which is in the village of Karuni. But it is possible that this method can be applied by schools with the same traditional home culture as *ummakalada*.

The application of the study tour method is carried out in three steps, namely 1) Planning Activities, 2) implementation activities, and 3) follow-up (Majid, 2013). these three steps become a reference for doing study tour at *ummakalada* as a living museum.

1. The first step: Planning Activities Before Visiting UmmaKalada

At this step the things that the teacher must pay attention to are; 1) formulate the objectives of the study tour. At this stage, the teacher examines the objectives of the social studies material to be achieved. The social studies material is adjusted to the social studies themes in the curriculum in elementary schools with the *ummakalada* value described in table 1 above; 2) determine the object of the study tour method. The object of tourism here is *ummakalada* which is located in *WannoKalada*, Karuni village, Loura district; 3) planning the duration of study tour activities at *ummakalada*. The duration of the study tour activities is adjusted to the topic to be achieved and takes into account the endurance of the students who are still in the process of growing towards physical maturity. 4) develop a study plan for students during study tours. At this stage the teacher arranges things that students will do while visiting the *ummakalada*. Whether students are formed in small groups, what questions or information are the focus during the study tour. In this section, students need to collect in advance to be able to prepare themselves related to study tours. 5) planning learning equipment that must be provided such as observation guidelines, interview guidelines, cameras and recording devices as well as the personal needs of students during study tours. Another thing that is a concern in this planning is the need to inform the study tour activities to related parties such as school principals and parents. The goal is that the implementation of tourism works can be achieved properly.

2. Second Step: Implementation

In this step, students and teachers do study tours in accordance with the previous planning stage. What time is the gathering, ensuring the completeness of the study tour and the physical readiness of students. At this stage the teacher ensures students to focus on the purpose of the study tour. Teacher guidance is very necessary.

3. Third Step: Follow Up Activities

This step is a form of follow-up when finished doing a study tour. What is done is that students are asked to make reports. Reports can be in the form of oral reports on the way home in the vehicle or in class. While the written report is done in groups or individually as homework or in class. The implementation of this study tour in addition to teaching students to learn directly related to the topic of social studies in elementary school at *ummakalada* but also fosters an attitude of cooperation, conflict resolution, leadership, critical thinking, and pride in the uniqueness of their culture.

Conclusion

Social studies in elementary school holds a very important position in helping students who grow and develop to become good citizens. This is supported by the level of development of the students who are in the training phase and imitate or are briefly easily steerable. The culture that students have becomes a strength in teaching social studies. The material for elementary social studies in the national curriculum deals with facts, concepts and theories that are closest to the students. Making the culture around students a source of learning is called ethnopedagogy.

The indigenous Loura people living on the island of Sumba in Indonesia still preserve the originality of their traditional house, namely *UmmaKalada*. *Ummakalada* means big house. It is said *ummakalada* because all members of the tribe descended from the same ancestor have things and obligations to uphold and maintain the traditional house (*ummakalada*).

The use of *UmmaKalada* as a learning resource for elementary social studies is done through the analysis of the basic material of elementary social studies in the national curriculum. After analyzing the material, social science issues were found in the *UmmaKalada*, namely culture, natural resources, religion, social groups and economic activities. The material can be taught using the field trip method. Students and teachers come to visit *UmmaKalada*. Due to the existence and views of *UmmaKalada* that have survived to this day, *UmmaKalada* can be used as a living museum.

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